

EmpowerUs

Socio-Economic Empowerment
of Coastal Communities

Deliverable 6.8: Website Version 1.0

20/12/2022

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ERINN Innovation Ltd

PUBLIC

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Executive Summary

The objective of Deliverable 6.8 (D6.8 – Website) is to provide an overview of the project website and its design and development by ERINN Innovation. The website will be hosted, managed and maintained by ERINN for the full duration of the project (October 2022 – September 2025) and will remain available for up to 5 years after the end for project (September 2030).

The main objective of the EmpowerUs project website is to facilitate communication and dissemination activities, as well as stakeholder engagement, by raising widespread awareness of and promoting the project’s objectives, activities and results over the full course of the project. It will be the main tool for promoting the project and disseminating results, resources and tools and will be updated regularly with news and events from the project.

The website went live in M3 (December 2022).

Website address: www.empowerus-project.eu

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1. Introduction

The project website is a key tool for promoting the project and disseminating the project's objectives, work plan and results to a wider audience, including all stakeholders and possible end-users. The website was developed following the EU's¹ best practice guidelines for European-funded project websites. The website is fully compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (EU 2016/679, GDPR) by incorporating a privacy statement and a pop-up informing website visitors about what the project does with any personal data gathered. Google analytics is used to track traffic and monitor the use of the website.

To ensure successful promotion of the project and to sustain the interest of the target audience and attract new users, the website's content will be maintained, continuously updated and populated with new information through the project's lifetime. It will comprise both technical details for those with a professional interest in the project and general information that will appeal to a broader range of stakeholders (e.g. local community groups, general public). The website will serve as a valuable public resource of research information on the subject and for promoting the outputs of publicly funded research in the domain beyond the project's lifetime.

The website has multiple roles as:

- A communication resource to promote the project, its objectives, the partnership, funding, project activities and results in research, industry, policy and public arenas.
- A communication resource to showcase results, key outcomes and major achievements and keep update interested parties on project progress.
- Provide a news portal for project news, notices, press releases, events, media resources, opportunities to get involved and updates from the project as well as associated projects and other initiatives.
- A platform and repository for public deliverables and outputs (data, reports and publications).

¹<https://enspire.science/guide-for-building-your-horizon-europe-projects-website-for-funded-projects-under-horizon-europe-and-erc/>

2. Development

An EmpowerUs website terms of reference document was developed by ERINN Innovation (in M1) outlining the criteria, technical specifications, style, aesthetics, and an overview of the website structure. Website wireframes were constructed (in M2) based on this document (see *Figure 1*). The project brand, colour scheme and imagery were added in the design phase (M2 - M3) and elements, based on the project logo, were constructed and integrated into the design (see *Figure 2*). Content and project information were added, and the final build phase was carried out (in M3), in which each page of the website was finalised.

Figure 1. Example of website wireframes

Figure 2. Website design phase

3. EmpowerUs Website

The EmpowerUs website structure follows an easy to use and intuitive pathway that allows the user to explore the website easily.

The **“Homepage”** contains links to the main pages on the website. It provides a short overview of what the project is about and encourages users to get involved through the featured opportunities and news articles. The top menu bar contains buttons leading to all the sections of the website. It also contains a **“Subscribe to News”** button, a **“Login”** button for project partners that links to the project SharePoint, a Search bar, social media buttons and a button for the project email (info@empowerus-project.eu). The footer on every page includes acknowledgement of EU funding as well as contact details for the project and links to the Data Policy and Privacy Statement.

The menu subpages under the **“About”** tab provide more information on what the project is about. The **“Project Overview”** subpage gives insights into the challenges that the project tackles, the main objectives of the project and the expected impacts that the project aims to achieve. The **“Work Packages”** subpage gives an overview of each of the seven work packages of the project.

The menu subpages under the **“Team”** tab provides information about the project partners and their roles in the project (**“Consortium”**), in addition to an overview of both the **“Steering Committee”** and the **“International Advisory Board”**.

The **“Transition Coastal Labs”** page provides an overview of the six Transition Coastal Labs that are involved in the project. Each lab has its own subpage that provides a description of the site, and specific information about the labs including an Introduction to each lab, the Challenges and Risks that exist, the planned Intervention in each lab and the Expected Outcomes of the intervention.

There are three further pages where website visitors can find more information:

- The **“News & Events”** page will be regularly updated with stories of interest relevant to the project, as well as project-related events and activities. This page will include news items about the EmpowerUs project and any external news relevant to EmpowerUs. Events organised by the EmpowerUs consortium, as well as events where EmpowerUs partners will be represented and any other events of interest to the partnership such as conferences and workshops related to EmpowerUs’ domain will also be included.
- The **“Results”** page will contain a list of the project deliverables, reports and scientific and peer-reviewed publications and any other significant outputs from the project as they become available.
- The **“Resources”** page, that contains press releases, links to project videos, promotional and dissemination materials and other project products.

Project Overview

The EmpowerUs project is a multi-country, multi-disciplinary research project that aims to explore the socio-economic impacts of coastal development and transformation. The project is led by the University of Southampton and involves partners from the UK, Norway, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Denmark, Estonia, Germany, Ireland, Spain and the UK.

At a glance

Programme	Marie Skłodowska Curie
Type of Action	ERC-Synergy Grant (under H2020)
Topic	Climate Change and Environmental Management
Duration	October 2022 - September 2025
Coordinator	Dr. Sarah E. Perkins
Coordinator	University of Southampton, UK
Total budget	€10,000,000 (ERC-Synergy Grant)

The Challenge

Coastal communities face many challenges that stem from the increasing risk of climate change. Rising sea levels, increased storm frequency and intensity, and ocean acidification are all threats that coastal communities face. These threats can have significant impacts on the socio-economic well-being of coastal communities, including loss of land, damage to infrastructure, and loss of livelihoods. The EmpowerUs project aims to explore the socio-economic impacts of coastal development and transformation, and to develop strategies to address these challenges.

Objectives

1. To explore the socio-economic impacts of coastal development and transformation.
2. To develop strategies to address the challenges of coastal development and transformation.
3. To build capacity and knowledge in coastal communities.
4. To promote sustainable coastal development and transformation.
5. To enhance the resilience of coastal communities.
6. To improve the quality of life in coastal communities.

Expected Impacts

The project is expected to have several impacts, including:

- Improved understanding of the socio-economic impacts of coastal development and transformation.
- Development of strategies to address the challenges of coastal development and transformation.
- Increased capacity and knowledge in coastal communities.
- Promotion of sustainable coastal development and transformation.
- Enhanced resilience of coastal communities.
- Improved quality of life in coastal communities.

01. Explore the socio-economic impacts of coastal development and transformation.

02. Develop strategies to address the challenges of coastal development and transformation.

03. Build capacity and knowledge in coastal communities.

04. Promote sustainable coastal development and transformation.

05. Enhance the resilience of coastal communities.

06. Improve the quality of life in coastal communities.

Work Packages

The EmpowerUs project is divided into seven work packages (WPs) that focus on different aspects of coastal development and transformation. Each WP is led by a different partner organization and involves a team of researchers and practitioners.

WP1 Project Management and Coordination

WP2 Transition Coastal Labs

WP3 Participatory Methods to Support Social Transition and Innovation

WP4 Evidence-based and Nature-based Solutions for Green Resilient Innovation

WP5 Systems of Inclusive Transition: Resilience and Sustainable Outcomes

WP6 Socio-Economic Resilience

WP7 Policy Implementation

Ensuring resilient, inclusive and sustainable coastal development

Key project outputs such as deliverables, outcomes, reports and spin-offs will be subject to the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

[Results](#)

Transition Coastal Labs

The Transition Coastal Labs (TCL) are a series of multi-stakeholder platforms that bring together researchers, practitioners, and community members to explore the socio-economic impacts of coastal development and transformation. The TCLs are designed to be inclusive and participatory, and to focus on developing strategies to address the challenges of coastal development and transformation.

Ensuring resilient, inclusive and sustainable coastal development

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[Results](#)

Contact Us

Project Coordinator: Sarah E. Perkins (s.e.perkins@soton.ac.uk)

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Communication & Press: Daniela Heath (d.heath@soton.ac.uk)

[Results](#)

Our Team

CONSORTIUM | STEERING COMMITTEE | INTERNATIONAL ADVISORY BOARD

Consortium

The EmpowerUs consortium is led by four research institutes (UK), Norway, and brings together 10 partner organisations from Bulgaria, Cyprus, Denmark, Estonia, Germany, Ireland, Spain and the UK.

Steering Committee

The Steering Committee is the supervisory body for the execution of the project. It consists of the EmpowerUs Project Coordinator, Work Package Leaders and the Gender, Equality and Diversity Coordinator. Each member is given one vote each in decision making for all project issues and will guide the dissemination of results that arise from the project.

International Advisory Board

The International Advisory Board consists of independent experts and policy makers with expertise on coastal development and transformation, whose involvement will ensure the gathering of additional expertise and knowledge necessary to assist the Consortium on strategic matters and give guidelines in order to maximise the impact of the project results.

News & Events

EmpowerUs Kick-off Meeting

04 Oct 2022

The EmpowerUs Kick-off Meeting took place at Southampton on 4th Oct 2022. The meeting included a series of presentations and discussions, and was a great opportunity for partners to co-develop concrete plans for the project.

EmpowerUs project launched to enable coastal communities to act for change

08 Oct 2022

The EmpowerUs project has been launched in a meeting in Southampton. The project aims to explore the socio-economic impacts of coastal development and transformation, and to develop strategies to address these challenges.

Contact Us

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Key project outputs such as deliverables, publications, reports and open access data will be added once they become available. This page will be updated regularly, so make sure to check back again soon!

EmpowerUs resources will be added here as they become available.

Figure 3. EmpowerUs Website screenshots

A “Tools” page and three subpages (Figure 4), accessible from the main menu, have been created on the website back-end. These pages are currently hidden from public view and will be made visible once the project tools become available. The following subpages will be included in this section:

- The “**EmpowerCoast Platform**” subpage, with information about the purpose of the platform (developed by ITS) and an external link to the platform.
- The “**EmpowerUs Story Map**” subpage, with an interactive map and blue justice stories from the Transition Coastal Lab sites.
- The “**Ocean Literacy**” subpage, which provides Ocean Literacy tools and resources.

Figure 4. Hidden “Tools” subpages

4. Conclusion

The *empowerus-project.eu* website domain was purchased (in M1) for eight years. A placeholder was added in M1 (October 2022) providing a brief summary of the project, contact information and links to the dedicated project social media channels.

The full and final website was live on 20th December 2022 (M3). Google analytics will be used to track traffic and monitor the use of the website (fully compliant with the GDPR) and will be regularly updated by ERINN Innovation the full duration of the and up to 5 years after the end for project.

Website address: www.empowerus-project.eu

EmpowerUs

Socio-Economic Empowerment
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